

EMPATHY IN DESIGN: A HEALTH CARE SERVICE DESIGN COLLABORATIVE WORKSHOP

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ABSTRACT

This paper is a descriptive and quality case study discussing how empathy in design research can inform the services offered in a healthcare environment. The research and design development process applies an empathy approach to a sponsored project by a public hospital from a student design team and course tutors' perspectives over a period of 14-week interaction design graduate studio workshop.

In this case study, the design team utilized human-centered design (IDEO, 2011) and empathy in design research frameworks (Kouprie & Visser, 2009; Chan & Sanders, 2004) defined by three key design phases: Discover, Conceptualizing, and Prototyping. The authors describe the tools, methods, and techniques that the design team applies to understand the ethnic minority patient experience; to define opportunities; to create concepts; and to deliver useful, usable and desirable design solutions (Sanders, 1992). The authors reflect on the workshop's learning objectives and the holistic approach to human-centered interaction design.

Keywords: empathy in design research, human-centered design, service design, interaction design, healthcare design.

INTRODUCTION: LEARNING OBJECTIVES AND PROJECT GOALS

Design is playing a larger role in crafting the experiences of our everyday lives. Designers are moving beyond defining physical and digital products

(Poggenpohl, 2009) to designing holistic emotional experiences that can be delivered by a product, a service, a message, or a large complex organization.

The aims of the interaction and service design studio workshop presented in this case study are focusing on "enhancing human ability and life through the design of innovative, interactive and experiential ideas, based on a synthesis of human thought patterns and habits with technical means" (Xin, 2011). A combination of theory, planning strategies, research, design skills establish the basis of the learning experience that explore emerging characteristics of interaction and service design, based on human needs and desires as well as innovative humanization of technologies.

The studio course syllabus was defined by three key design phases: Discover, Conceptualizing, and Prototyping over a period of 14-week semester. The processes emphasized the human-centered and iterative design approach that started with understanding the wants, needs and limitations of the end user and the service provider. The discovered insights allowed the team to identify and define problems of interaction and service. The second phase of the process focused on creating concepts and solutions that are relevant to the defined problems by altering users, actions, means, context and purpose of the scenario. The final phase of the project was communicating and demonstrating the proposed solution in a use-case scenario. The process was a multidisciplinary collaboration with graduate students from different design backgrounds, health care specialists and administrators, design practitioners, and educators to enrich the teaching and learning experience in a real-world context.

Figure 1. Design Research Matrix – Organizing and Presenting Findings and Insights

The main focus of the sponsored project was to identify design challenge and create interaction and service design solutions to enhance the experience of Ethnic Minority (EM) patients in a public hospital environment—Special Out Patient Department (SOPD), Ambulatory Service Center (ASC), Accident and Emergency Department (AED). The target stakeholders were Pakistani and Nepalese women who live in Hong Kong with their families. The other stakeholders also included the family members of these women, the clinic doctors, nurses, and staff. The proposed design solutions considered both digital information technology and conventional humanized approaches.

DISCOVER

The discover phase of this studio workshop involved emotional and rational explorations of the current reality, identifying design problems, understanding stakeholders' needs and inspirations. A visit to the hospital was arranged, where the design team was given an orientation of the facilities and their services.

The team met with administrators, doctors, nurses, and staff at an introduction session, where the sponsor presented the current situations and design challenge from the organization's perspective. The hospital also provided privacy and volunteer training for the students so they could establish contact and formal procedures for generative research to be conducted on-site with the stakeholders.

This design team formulated a qualitative research plan with the goal of understanding the clinic experience from different perspectives and contexts considering a range of activities, environment, interactions, services, objects, and stakeholders. The plan guided the team to strategically design the “who, what, where, and how” of the research activities including interviews, observations, shadowing, and cultural probes.

A series of interviews were conducted with three different departments at the hospital—SOPD, ASC, AED. Doctors, nurses, and staff were engaged in

these one-on-one and small group interviews. Their concerns ranging from helping EM patients to understand what they need to do and where they need to go within their patients' journey at SOPD; educating EM patients about the preparation before the medical operations; guiding EM patients in communicating their pain after the medical operation; dealing with the language barrier at AED when no interpreter is available; and other areas relating to cultural and religious issues.

Communicating directly with the EM patients was a complex task for the research team deal to the language barrier, research ethical issue, and scheduling challenge. Restricted observation and shadowing the interactions of the EM patents with the doctor, interpreter, and hospital staff were conducted to allow the research team members to develop a deeper empathy for whom they are designing.

Data collected during these interviews and observations allowed the design team to develop a patient experience map informing the next phase of the design process. The team utilized a design research matrix in organizing and analysis the key data collected. It is also used as a framework to facilitate the team in identifying patterns and problems and for presenting proposed design opportunities (Figure 1). This framework also served as a unified format across all design teams in the workshop for presenting their research findings to the class and sponsored clients.

CONCEPTUALIZING

The conceptualizing phase involved the design team to shift from research to develop possible solutions. The designers went through a process of synthesis and interpretation. "This requires a mode of narrowing and culling information and translating insights about the reality of today into a set of opportunities for the future" (IDEO, 2011). The various processes of defining the design opportunities were overlapped with the data analysis of the discover phase and the initial concept development phase. The graduate students engaged in critique and brainstorming sessions to identify and understand the big picture, to gain aspirations for the future, and to envision the

'What If' scenarios (Liedtka & Ogilvie, 2011; Schneider & Stickdorn, 2010). They refined patient experience map (Figure 2), and developed mind mapping diagrams, user profiles and personas, and scenario and storyboard outlines (Figure 3).

The patient experience map, a type of customer journey, provided a context for design concept development by identifying, documenting and communicating the hospital service experience; visualizing various layers and dimensions of interaction with medical staff; understanding the factors influencing stockholders; and identifying design opportunities for concept development.

The design team defined and visualized a specific use-case scenario of the patient journey in the existing interaction model, which provided them a macro view of the service interaction in specific contexts. Students developed a preferred interaction model and continued to refine their understanding of

Current Patient Experience

Figure 2: Brainstorming Sessions Outcome: Patient Experience Map

Figure 3: Brainstorming Sessions Outcome: Scenarios

the wants, needs and limitations of the various stockholders, gaining insight from feedback provided by the hospital team, tutors, and peers. This process helped them to develop design strategies, concepts, interaction and service models, and prototypes.

PROTOTYPING

“Prototyping is about building to think, acknowledging that the process of making ideas real and tangible” (IDEO, 2011). It is an efficient and effective methodology and iterative set of activities that allows the design team to visualize, clarify, interact, and refine design concepts. The design team translated the identified design opportunities into high-level insights and developed a series of design concept prototype forms ranging from sketches, card sorting, flowcharts, storyboards, information architecture, user interface, interaction model, and concept videos, or digital walkthroughs providing photo sequencing, animation and motion graphic depiction of the proposed interactions and services (Figure 4).

The final proposed design concept “Pre-operative Assessment Live Management” (PALM) was demonstrated as an interactive prototype for a tablet computer application format. The design team described the new PALM as a tool that would facilitate better and more direct communication between patients and doctors. The main functions of this system include signing in, itinerary, consultation, instruction, and agenda. Four unique attributes (Figure 5) are highlighted during the prototype presentation to hospital team and the class:

1. Benefits Two Sides—During consultation the PALM screen splits into two parts, one side for the patient and the other side for the medical staff. Both sides contain relevant cue cards that can be operated in a less interaction level for the EM patient, and a higher interaction level for the doctor or the nurse. PALM can provide voice instructions and show exact information on both sides with bilingual display.

Figure 4: Prototypes: Information Architecture, User Interface, Interaction Model, and Concept Video

2. Cue Cards—The pentagon shape cue cards present relevant instructions, keywords, and symbols. The unique shape supports a more intuitive way to make connection and grouping of similar instructions. The cue card can activate the PALM device's voice feature.
3. Agenda—A customized agenda programmed by medical staff at designated patient service station provides step-by-step pre-surgery instructions for EM patients a week prior to the operation that they can take home.
4. Multi-platform—The PALM system operates on three platforms, including tablets, websites, and paper cue cards to facilitate every aspect of the patient's experience and accommodates varied user skills and technology familiarity.

Figure 5: Four Unique Design Attributes of PALM

REFLECTIONS AND CONCLUSION

This case study presents the design process, proposed solutions and learning experience of three graduate students constituting the design team, during their first term's design studio workshop of a master degree program in Interaction Design. It also reflects the main objectives of the program that: "1) putting people first in the people/technology equation by exploring human-centeredness, 2) understanding active communication processes on which interactivity is built, 3) learning methods for analysis and construction of interaction design, 4) working across communication technology, product interface, or

service systems, and finally 5) developing a holistic approach to human-centered interaction that includes problem or opportunity identification, research, prototyping, and execution" (Xin, 2011).

The authors interacted with the design team as tutors, facilitators, and project managers during this 14-week sponsored project. The design participants of this project concluded that the key components throughout the process were to identify design opportunities, develop insight, and create solutions through deep understanding of the context of the problems and empathy in designing for the various stakeholders.

The authors learned that to obtain empathic understanding of the problems is challenging for the sponsor, design team, and tutors—it requires sufficient resource and effort, it demands both rational analysis and emotional connection, it needs specific skills and design thinking, it calls for open-mindedness and discipline, and it involves multiple perspectives and cultural interpretations.

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